

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Package

INPP5D (SHIP1) v1

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Bioinformatics

Introduction

As the bioinformatic core of TREAT-AD target prioritization, we have performed a series of analyses on drug target INPP5D/SHIP1. These analyses include both data driven hypothesis generation using genome-wide transcriptomic and epigenomic data as well as targeted study on INPP5D based on pathway analysis and differential expression analysis. The hypothesis generation process is also an interactive process with input from other cores in the IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center based on various selection criteria which will be discussed in the later sections of this report. In addition, there are additional target candidates going through a similar selection process.

Frequent gene co-expression network mining identified microglia specific gene modules in AD

Gene co-expression network analysis is a powerful bioinformatics tool to identify genes that are involved in common biological processes, regulatory networks, and cell-specific expression. Given the large amount of publicly available gene expression datasets for AD, an important question is: are there any genes that show strong co-expression relationships in AD and human brains? By identifying genes that are co-expressed in AD, we can identify potential AD specific processes and cell types. To ensure the robustness of the analysis, we have established a

mature pipeline and co-expression network mining algorithm for identifying frequently co-expressed gene modules using multiple datasets¹⁻³. We have previously mined frequently co-expressed gene modules for AD using 3-5 datasets^{4,5} and identified multiple co-expressed gene modules in AD. Here, we further expanded the frequent network mining using eight large datasets as listed in Table 1.

Table 1 | AD and normal brain transcriptomic datasets.

Dataset	AD samples	Normal samples	Brain region
GSE5281	87	74	Middle Temporal Gyrus (MTG), Posterior Cingulate Cortex (PCC), Entorhinal Cortex (EC), Hippocampus (HC), Superior Frontal Cortex (SFG), Primary Visual Cortex (VCX)
GSE48350	80	173	Entorhinal Cortex (EC), Post-central Gyrus (PCG2), Superior Frontal Gyrus (SFG), Hippocampus (HC)
GSE33000	310	157	Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex(DLPFC)
GSE44772	387	129	Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex (DLPFC), Visual Cortex (VC)
ROSMAP	224	201	Dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DLPFC)
MSBB	409	273	Frontal pole (BM10), Superior temporal gyrus (BM22), Parahippocampal gyrus (BM36), Inferior frontal gyrus (BM44)
Mayo	82	78	Temporal cortex (TC)
ABA	30	56	Hippocampus(HC), Temporal Cortex (TCx), Parietal Cortex(PC), Forebrain White Matter(FWM)

By applying the algorithm and process developed in Johnson, T.S., et al.⁴, we identified multiple frequently co-expressed gene modules. Table 2 shows two gene modules most significantly enriched in microglia-related biological processes.

Table 2. Gene modules that are strongly enriched with microglia genes. Red genes are potential candidate genes proposed by the center. The left module is identified using AD brain samples and the right module is from normal brain samples.

AD3_8Data_freq_0.05_unnormalized_0.74	N5_8Data_freq_0.05_unnormalized_0.74
ABI3, ARHGAP30, ARHGDIB, ARPC1B, BTK, C1QA, C1QB, C3, C3AR1, CD300A, CD74, CD86, CSF1R , CSF3R, CTSS, CYBA, CYBB, CYTL1, DOCK2, DOCK8, FCGR2A, FLI1, FPR1, GIMAP4, GIMAP6, GIMAP8, GPM3, HAVCR2, HCK, HCLS1, HLA-DMB, HLA-DOA, HLA-DRA, IFI30, IL10RA, INPP5D , ITGAM, ITGB2, LAIR1, LCP1, LGALS9, LILRA2, LY86, MFNG, MS4A4A, MS4A6A, MS4A7, MYO1F, NCKAP1L, PIK3AP1, PLCG2 , PLEK, PTPN6, PTPRC, RHBDF2, RNASE6, SERPINA1, SIPA1, SLA, SLC1A5, SLC2A5, SLC7A7, SLCO2B1, STK10, SYK, TAL1, TBXAS1, TLR2, TLR7, TMEM119, TREM2, TYROBP , VAV1, VSIG4, WAS, WDFY4	PLEK, LAT2, BTK, ITGB2, STEAP3, LCP1, CD86, PTPRC, PYGL, HLA-DMB, HCLS1, CD14, LY86, C3, CYBA, TYROBP, PIK3AP1, HLA-DRA, AIF1, BLNK, SYK, SLC1A5, SLC2A5, CYBB, NCKAP1L, DOCK8, HCK, TREM2, C1QA, SLA, ITGAM, FCGR2A, SCIN, WDFY4, IFI30, SERPINA1, MS4A6A, STAB1, FCGR1A, PARP9, LAIR1, DOCK2, CD300A, C1QB, FPR1, ALPK1, CASP1, CCR1, TBXAS1

While both gene modules are enriched in microglia functions, the AD module is much larger with important genes such as INPP5D and PLCG2. Both gene modules contain well-known AD genes such as TREM2. Pathway analysis using Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA) also confirmed the AD gene module is highly enriched in immune function genes, as shown in the figure on the right.

INPP5D is specifically expressed in AD brains

An ideal target will be genes with low expression levels in normal brain tissues while high in AD brains. We first checked the gene expression levels for a selected group of genes of interest. As shown in the figure below, among all tissues, INPP5D is highly expressed in EBV-transformed lymphocytes, spleen, whole blood and small intestine. INPP5D has very low expression levels in normal brain tissues. Furthermore, the brain regions with relatively higher INPP5D are not focal areas of AD (i.e., substantia nigra, hypothalamus).

Genes	Brain Expression in general (FPKM)	Highest Expression in Brain	High Expression in Tissues
INPP5D	Low (5-20)	Spinal cord, substantia nigra, hypothalamus	EBV-transformed lymphocytes, spleen, whole blood, small intestine
PLCG2	Extremely low (2-4)	Spinal cord, substantia nigra, basal ganglia	EBV-transformed lymphocytes, spleen, whole blood, small intestine
CSF1R	Medium (<50)	Spinal cord, substantia nigra	spleen
STAT3	Medium (<50)	Spinal cord, cerebellar hemisphere	All other tissues except brain
ABCA7	Medium (<50)	Cerebellar hemisphere, cerebellum	Whole blood, pituitary, spleen
PTK2B	High (>100)	Cerebellar hemisphere, cerebellum	Brain, EBV-transformed lymphocytes, whole blood

We further compared gene expression levels of INPP5D between AD and normal tissues in five datasets and results are summarized in Table 3. In all five datasets, INPP5D is significantly overexpressed in AD brain samples with fold-change ranges from 1.2 to 1.5.

Table 3. Differential gene expression analysis for INPP5D

Dataset	log2 FC AD vs. Normal	Ave Expression levels	t-stat	P.Value	adj.P.Val
GSE48350	0.387745841	8.134132818	6.042989852	5.35E-09	1.19E-07
GSE5281	0.628882854	4.433585413	7.383595196	7.12E-12	1.69E-10
MSBB	0.498083953	4.101808234	8.924332217	4.05E-18	8.58E-16
ROSMAP	0.26063898	2.57548141	4.72332342	3.15E-06	0.00018639
GSE33000	0.577774108	1.165034887	13.84229345	9.43E-37	1.15E-35

INPP5D functions as a hub gene in immune response networks

We searched IPA for potential regulation, interactions, and pathway intersections between INPP5D/SHIP1 and the rest of the Year1 target candidates including PLCG2 (See figure below). IPA analysis identified that INPP5D/SHIP1 functions as a hub to link PLCG2, TYROBP, IL10 and several other immune response genes/proteins.

For the IPA canonical pathways involving INPP5D and PLCG by IPA, analysis showed the two are involved in multiple immune response pathways and phagosome formation. The x-axis of the figure is in the $-\log_{10}$ scale; and thus, the larger the number, the smaller the p-value for the enrichment analysis.

Canonical Pathways from IPA

Using the ToppGene tool, we also identified key pathways in which the selected genes are highly enriched, as shown below, which include interleukin signaling pathway, cytokine signaling pathway and functions in the adaptive immune system.

Targets involved pathways

Pathway	Source	No. Mol.	Total	Involved targets
IL-10 Anti-inflammatory Signaling Pathway	MSigDB C2 BIOCARTA (v6.0)	4	17	IL10,IL10RA,STAT3,STAT4
Interleukin signaling pathway	PantherDB	5	92	SPI1,IL10,IL10RA,STAT3,STAT4
IL22 Soluble Receptor Signaling Pathway	MSigDB C2 BIOCARTA (v6.0)	3	16	IL10RA,STAT3,STAT4
Signaling by Interleukins	BioSystems: REACTOME	7	531	IL10,PDGFA,IL10RA,IL1RAP,PTK2B,INPP5D,STAT3
Epstein-Barr virus infection	BioSystems: KEGG	5	203	SPI1,IL10,IL10RA,STAT3,PLCG2
PDGF signaling pathway	PantherDB	4	127	PDGFA,STAT3,STAT4,PLCG2
Cytokine Signaling in Immune system	BioSystems: REACTOME	7	763	IL10,PDGFA,IL10RA,IL1RAP,PTK2B,INPP5D,STAT3
Osteoclast differentiation	BioSystems: KEGG	4	130	SPI1,TREM2,TYROBP,PLCG2
Bioactive Peptide Induced Signaling Pathway	MSigDB C2 BIOCARTA (v6.0)	3	43	PTK2B,STAT3,STAT4
Jak-STAT signaling pathway	BioSystems: KEGG	4	156	IL10,IL10RA,STAT3,STAT4
Signal regulatory protein (SIRP) family interactions	BioSystems: REACTOME	2	13	PTK2B,TYROBP
EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitor resistance	BioSystems: KEGG	3	79	PDGFA,STAT3,PLCG2
JAK/STAT signaling pathway	PantherDB	2	16	STAT3,STAT4
Other semaphorin interactions	BioSystems: REACTOME	2	19	TREM2,TYROBP
Cytokine-cytokine receptor interaction	BioSystems: KEGG	4	270	IL10,PDGFA,IL10RA,IL1RAP
Adaptive Immune System	BioSystems: REACTOME	6	826	TREM2,PDGFA,TYROBP,CD33,INPP5D,PLCG2

INPP5D interacts with key immune response genes and kinases

In addition, we searched the STRING protein-protein interaction database for INPP5D focusing on proteins/genes with immediate interactions. As shown in the figure, INPP5D is a hub of the PPI network in the STRING database, tightly interacting with TIGIT, KLRG1, GRB2, PIK3R1, ITPKB, FCGR2B, PTPN6, SHC1, PTPN11, BTK, many of them are involved in immune response or protein kinase/phosphatase activity.

The interacting proteins/genes are listed below with their functions and type of interactions.

Your Input:

INPP5D
Phosphatidylinositol 3,4,5-trisphosphate 5-phosphatase 1; Phosphatidylinositol (PtdIns) phosphatase that specifically hydrolyzes the 5-phosphate of phosphatidylinositol-3,4,5-trisphosphate (PtdIns(3,4,5)P3) to produce PtdIns(3,4)P2, thereby negatively regulating the PI3K (phosphoinositide 3-kinase) pathways. Acts as a negative regulator of B-cell antigen receptor signaling. Mediates signaling from the FC-gamma-RIIB receptor (FCGR2B), playing a central role in terminating signal transduction from activating immune/hematopoietic cell receptor systems. Acts as a negative regulator of mye [...] (1189 aa)

Predicted Functional Partners:

		Neighborhood	Gene Fusion	Cooccurrence	Coexpression	Experiments	Databases	Textmining	Homology/	Score
SHC1	SHC-transforming protein 1; Signaling adapter that couples activated growth factor receptors to signaling pathways. Participat...									0.999
FCGR2B	Low affinity immunoglobulin gamma Fc region receptor II-b; Receptor for the Fc region of complexed or aggregated immunogl...									0.998
GRB2	Growth factor receptor-bound protein 2; Adapter protein that provides a critical link between cell surface growth factor recepto...									0.991
DOK1	Docking protein 1; DOK proteins are enzymatically inert adaptor or scaffolding proteins. They provide a docking platform for th...									0.986
KLRG1	Killer cell lectin-like receptor subfamily G member 1; Plays an inhibitory role on natural killer (NK) cells and T-cell functions upo...									0.966
TIGIT	T-cell immunoreceptor with Ig and ITIM domains; Binds with high affinity to the poliovirus receptor (PVR) which causes increas...									0.963
ITPKB	Inositol-trisphosphate 3-kinase B									0.962
PIK3R1	Phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase regulatory subunit alpha; Binds to activated (phosphorylated) protein-Tyr kinases, through its SH...									0.962
BTK	Tyrosine-protein kinase BTK; Non-receptor tyrosine kinase indispensable for B lymphocyte development, differentiation and sig...									0.962
PTPN11	Tyrosine-protein phosphatase non-receptor type 11; Acts downstream of various receptor and cytoplasmic protein tyrosine kin...									0.960

ToppGene analysis also revealed multiple interactions with pathways of JAK1, CSF1R, SYK, PTPN11, PIK3R1.

Interaction	No. Mol.	Total Mol.	Involved targets
JAK1 interactions	5	129	IL10RA,PTK2B,INPP5D,STAT3,PLCG2
CSF1R interactions	4	47	SPI1,INPP5D,STAT3,PLCG2
SYK interactions	5	141	PTK2B,TYROBP,INPP5D,STAT3,PLCG2
TYROBP interactions	3	19	TREM2,TYROBP,INPP5D
PTPN11 interactions	5	253	PTK2B,CD33,INPP5D,STAT3,PLCG2
PIK3R1 interactions	5	319	IL1RAP,PTK2B,INPP5D,STAT3,PLCG2
IL10RA interactions	2	5	IL10,IL10RA

INPP5D/SHIP1 interaction with the inflammasome (Pycard, NALP1, caspase-1, caspase-5)

IPA analysis revealed INPP5D is indirectly linked to inflammasome members through multiple types of Ig proteins. Please see figure below.

IPA network showing possible interactions between inflammasome with our drug targets

Immediate up/downstream interacting molecules from canonical pathways in IPA

Protein Constructs

Proteins Purified

The INPP5D gene is a member of the inositol polyphosphate-5-phosphatase (INPP5) family that encodes proteins called the Src homology 2-containing-inositol-phosphatases (SHIP). The complete, full-length SHIP1 protein contains at least 5-domains that are designated as; 1.) the N-terminal SH2 domain (SH2), 2.) the PH-L, 3.) the inositol phosphatase catalytic domain (Ptase), 4.) the C2 domain and 5.) the C-terminal domain containing PXXP and NPXY motifs (*Figure 1*). Several different SHIP1 expression constructs have been generated that contain different domains of the SHIP1 protein (*Table 4, Figure 1*.) Construct 4 that encodes the Phosphatase and C2 domains of SHIP1 (Ptase-C2) has primarily been used for biochemical and crystallographic studies. This Ptase-C2 domain has been routinely produced using a baculovirus expression system. A typical yield of 4 mg of SHIP1 Ptase-C2 protein can be obtained from 1L of 2×10^6 SF9 cells/mL infected culture. All other constructs yield roughly the same amount or more protein from 1L of 2×10^6 SF9 cells/mL infected culture. Final purity results of each construct can be found in *Figure 2*.

Biophysical Characterization

The quaternary structure of the SHIP1 protein constructs listed in Table 4 were analyzed by size-exclusion chromatography coupled with multi-angle light scattering (SEC-MALS) and Mass-Photometry (REFEYN, Inc.) Analysis of the results from both approaches indicate that the two SHIP1 protein constructs, Ptase-C2 and PH-Ptase-C2, exist as monomers in solution at concentrations ranging from nanomolar (Mass Photometry) to micromolar (SEC-MALS). The SHIP1 protein construct containing four domains, SH2-PH-Ptase-C2, was surprisingly observed to exist as a tightly associated dimer over the low nanomolar (10 to 20 nM) to micromolar concentration range (*Figure 4*.) SEC-MALS analysis was performed on purified full-length SHIP1,

however, while the protein is soluble, the SEC-MALS results indicate the protein tends to form aggregates (*Figure 5.*)

Crystallization and X-ray Structural Analysis:

The two domain SHIP1 protein construct, Ptase-C2, was found to crystallize under similar conditions as reported for SHIP1 reported in the Protein Databank (PDB code: 6IBD). Reproducible crystals can be grown from a reservoir solution containing 17-22% PEG 2000MME, 7-10% PEG 3000, 0.1M BIS-Tris @pH 7.0.) An X-ray structure of SHIP1 with no ligands bound was determined to 2.1 Å resolution. In addition, the X-ray structure of Magnesium(II)-phosphate bound structure was determined to 1.6 Å (*Figure 6.*) Multiple attempts were made to determine X-ray structures of SHIP1 Ptase-C2 bound to designed and synthesized ligands via co-crystallization and co-crystallization approaches to no avail. Strong electron density consistent with a bound ligand was not obtained using the crystallization conditions described for PDB:6IBD. Using a modified version of the crystallization solution that contained 17-22% PEG 2000MME, 7-10% PEG 3000, 0.1M HEPES pH 7.0, we were ultimately able to determine a ligand-bound structure (*Figure 6.*)

Future Plans

We will continue to use the SHIP1 Ptase-C2 protein construct and optimize crystallization conditions to obtain ligand-bound X-ray structures. Additionally, all other SHIP1 constructs (*Table 4*) will be subjected to sparse-matrix crystallization screens to identify crystallization conditions for both unbound and ligand-bound proteins.

Conclusion

Thus far, we have shown that the SHIP1 constructs in Table 4 can be successfully expressed and purified using a baculovirus expression system. While the full-length SHIP1 construct can be expressed and purified, SEC-MALS analysis indicates the protein is aggregated. Additionally, the SHIP1 four-domain construct, SH2-PH-Ptase-C2, exists as a tightly associated dimer in solution. Lastly, using a modified version of crystallization conditions reported for PDB:6IBD, high-resolution ligand-bound X-ray crystal structures of the Ptase-C2 domain can be obtained.

Methods:

Generation of baculovirus viral stocks for the expression and purification of SHIP1 proteins:

SHIP1 (Ptase-C2) Bacmid Generation: A baculovirus transfer vector encoding SHIP1's Phosphatase and C2 (Ptase-C2) domain (*Figure 1*), gifted by Dr. Opher Gileadi, was transposed into Bacmid DNA following Invitrogen's Bac-to-Bac baculovirus expression protocol. All procedures were carried out in a sterile environment around an open flame.

SHIP1 (Ptase-C2) P0 viral stock generation: Viral stocks were generated using a modified version of Dr. Opher Gileadi's protein production in insect cells protocol. All procedures were carried out in a BSL2 grade bio-safety cabinet. 1 mL of 4×10^5 SF9 II cell/mL (viability > 95%) in Gibco SF9 II Serum-Free media were transferred to a sterile 6-well plate. Cell viability was verified using a Bio-Rad automated cell counter. 5 μ L (2-3ug) of Bacmid DNA was transferred to 100 μ L of Grace's insect medium (GM). 2-4 μ L cellfectin II was transferred to 100 μ L of GM. Both Bacmid and cellfectin II solutions were mixed and incubated at room temperature for 45 minutes. Cellfectin II without the addition of bacmid DNA served as the negative control and was diluted in 200 μ L of GM. All samples were diluted with an additional 200 μ L of GM and immediately transferred to their corresponding wells. Transfection took place over 96 hours in an incubator set at 27 °C. After transfection had taken place, the P0 viral stock (supernatant) was harvested and centrifuged for 10 minutes at 700 x g to pellet any dead cells. The clarified P0 viral stock was then transferred to a clean 2 mL microcentrifuge tube and stored in the 4 °C for future use.

SHIP1 (Ptase-C2) P1 viral stock generation: 3 mL of 1×10^6 SF9 II cell/mL (viability > 95%) were transferred to a sterile 6-well plate. 120 μ L of P0 viral stock and cellfectin II control were transferred to their corresponding wells. P1 viral stock generation took place over 72 hours in an incubator set at 27 °C. After the allotted time, solutions were transferred to sterile 15 mL conical tubes and centrifuged for 10 minutes at 700 x g to pellet any cell debris. The P1 viral stocks (supernatant) were transferred to new, sterile 15 mL conical tubes and stored at 4 °C for future use.

1 mL of Buffer A (Table 5) was added to each well after removing the P1 viral stocks. Cells were resuspended by pipetting up and down with a P1000 and the solutions were transferred to clean 2 mL microcentrifuge tubes. Samples were placed at -80 °C overnight and thawed at room temperature the following day. Cell solutions were centrifuged at 13,000 x g for 10 minutes using a tabletop centrifuge. Protein concentration for soluble and insoluble fractions were determined using Bradford assay. SHIP1 Ptase-C2 expression was verified using SDS-PAGE (*Figure 3a.*)

SHIP1 (Ptase-C2) P2 viral stock generation: P2 viral stock generation was performed in suspension cultures using 20 mL of 1×10^6 SF9 II cell/mL (viability > 95%) in 125 mL Erlenmeyer flasks. 100 μ L of P1 viral stock was transferred to its corresponding suspension culture and incubated in a floor incubator set at 27 °C and 120 rpm (*Figure 3b.*) After a 72-hour incubation period, solutions were transferred to sterile 50 mL conical tubes and centrifuged for 15 minutes at 700 x g to pellet the cells. The P2 viral stocks (supernatant) were transferred to new, sterile 50 mL conical tubes and stored at 4 °C for future use.

5 mL of Buffer A was added to each tube containing pelleted P2 viral stocks cells. Cells were resuspended using a serological pipet. Samples were placed at -80 °C overnight and thawed at room temperature the following day. Cell solutions were centrifuged at 25,000 rpm

using a floor centrifuge for 30 minutes. Protein concentration for soluble and insoluble fractions were determined using Bradford assay. SHIP1 Ptase-C2 expression was verified using SDS-PAGE (*Figure 3b.*)

SHIP1 (Ptase-C2) Large Scale Expression: SHIP1 Ptase-C2 large scale expression was performed using 500 mL of 2×10^6 SF9 II cell/mL (viability > 95%) in 2000 mL Erlenmeyer flasks. 1 mL of P2 viral stock was transferred to each large-scale suspension culture. Infection took place over 72 hours in a floor incubator set at 27 °C with shaking at 120 rpm. After the 72-hr. period, cell count, morphology, and viability were checked to verify whether infection had taken place. Proper infection is observed by a reduction in cell doubling time, swollen cells, and a cell viability between 80-90%. Cells were transferred to 1L centrifuge bottles and centrifuged for 30 minutes at 700 x g. 120 mL of Buffer A was used to resuspend 1L of infected cells. Cell solutions were transferred to clean, sterile 50 mL conical tubes and placed at -80 °C for future use.

SHIP1 Genscript P2 viral stocks and expression: P2 viral stocks for the remaining constructs were generated by Genscript (Piscataway, NJ.) Expression of SHIP1 constructs PH-Ptase-C2 and SH2-PH-Ptase-C2 (*Figure 1*) were performed in 2L Erlenmeyer flasks containing 500 mL of 2×10^6 SF9 II cell/mL (viability > 95%). The volume of P2 viral stock was adjusted so that all cultures were infected with enough virus to equal 0.1 multiplicity of infection (M.O.I.) Viral infection took place over the course of 72 hours in a floor shaker set at 27 °C with shaking at 120 rpm. Cell count, morphology, and viability were checked to verify infection had taken place over the allotted time period. Cultures were transferred to 1L centrifuge bottles and centrifuged at 700 x g for 30 minutes. Cell media was decanted into a solution of 10% bleach and alconox. Cell solutions were resuspended in 120 mL Buffer A and placed into the -80 °C for future use.

SHIP1 Clarified Cell Lysate: All SHIP1 constructs were purified using similar buffers and purification methods. Purification buffers can be found in Table 5. In general, cell solutions were thawed at room temperature and shaken until a slushy consistency was obtained. The solutions were then sonicated on ice using a Branson Sonifier for 3 minutes at 50% amplitude for 6 seconds on and 9 seconds off. A clarified cell lysate was obtained after sonication by centrifuging the cell solution for 30-45 minutes at 25,000 rpm and 4 °C. Samples were then passed through a 0.45 µm filter before proceeding with IMAC.

Immobilized Metal Affinity Chromatography (IMAC) Batch Purification: Clarified cell lysates were incubated with 2-3 mL of HisPur™ Ni-NTA resin (Thermo Scientific) for 1-2 hours at 4 °C in a 250 mL container. The solutions were then centrifuged for 5 minutes at 400 x g to pellet the Nickel resin. The supernatant was decanted into a separate container (flow-through) and the resin was resuspended in 10-15 mL of buffer A. This process was performed several times until the supernatant was clear. The Nickel resin solution was transferred to a gravity filtration column at 4 °C and the remaining buffer A solution was allowed to flow-through until a small amount of liquid remained in the column. The column was washed with a solution containing 90% buffer A and 10% buffer B (*Table 5*) several times. All contents were collected in

a clean 50 mL conical tube (wash.) SHIP1 protein was eluted from the Nickel resin using 10-30 mL of 100% buffer B. Protein concentration and purity were determined using the Bradford assay and SDS-PAGE analysis. Fractions that contained SHIP1 were pooled together and 0.5-1 mg of Tobacco-etch virus (TEV) protease was added to the pooled protein. The SHIP1-TEV protein mixture was then placed into dialysis (TEV) overnight at 4 °C to facilitate removal of the N-terminal His-tag and excess imidazole.

After overnight dialysis, the protein sample was incubated with 1-2 mL of nickel resin for 15 minutes and then transferred to a clean gravity column. The solution was allowed to flow through the column and the solution was collected in a clean 50 mL conical tube. The nickel resin was rinsed with 5-10 mL of buffer A. The remaining protein bound to the nickel resin was eluted using 20 mL of 100% Buffer B. Protein concentration was determined using Bradford assay and the presence of SHIP1 was determined using SDS-PAGE.

IMAC FPLC Purification: Clarified cell lysates were run on an AKTA pure FPLC attached to a 5 mL Ni-HiTrap HP column (GE Healthcare.) After the lysate was fully loaded, the column was rinsed with buffer A until the absorbance at 280 nm returned to baseline. Samples were then washed with 10% Buffer B to remove any non-specific binders to the Nickel resin. SHIP1 protein was eluted using a 0-100% linear gradient of buffer A to B over 15 minutes at a flow rate of 2.5 mL/min. Protein concentration, purity, and removal of the N-terminal His-tag were facilitated using previously described methods (IMAC Batch Binding.)

After overnight dialysis, the protein solution was reloaded onto the 5 mL His-trap column. Flowthrough was collected in 12 mL fractions using the fraction collector. Remaining protein bound to the 5 mL His-trap column was removed with 100% buffer B. Protein concentration was determined using Bradford assay and the presence and purity of SHIP1 in the flowthrough was verified using SDS-PAGE.

SHIP1 Storage and Additional Purification: After isolating SHIP1 protein using IMAC chromatography, samples were concentrated, and buffer exchanged into buffer E (Table 5.) The samples were then flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 °C for future use. If the SHIP1 sample was judged to be < 85% pure, an additional purification step was added that involved either strong anion-exchange or gel-filtration chromatography. Note that anion exchange chromatography was only performed on the SHIP1 Ptase-C2 and PH-Ptase-C2 protein constructs. The SHIP1 SH2-PH-Ptase-C2 four-domain construct does not remain soluble in salt concentrations required for anion-exchange.

Anion Exchange Chromatography (MonoQ): Anion exchange chromatography was performed on SHIP1 constructs Ptase-C2 and PH-Ptase-C2 if the desired purity (> 90% pure) was not obtained after IMAC chromatography. Protein solutions were placed into anion exchange dialysis buffer (Table 5) to lower the conductivity of the solutions to 2-4 ms/cm. Protein solutions were then loaded onto an 8 mL MonoQ™ 10/100 column (Cytiva.) After all of the solution was loaded, protein elution occurred over 2-3 hours using a gradient of 0-50% buffer C

to D at a flow rate of 2 mL/min. Protein concentration was determined using Bradford assay and purity of SHIP1 was verified using SDS-PAGE.

Gel Filtration Chromatography: Gel filtration chromatography was performed on all samples prior to any biophysical analysis. Protein solutions were concentrated to 1-2.5 mL and loaded onto a 24 mL Superdex 200 Increase 10/300 GL column (Cytiva.) Depending on the biophysical analysis, the column was equilibrated with a buffer listed in *Table 5*. Protein concentrations were determined using a Biotek Take3 and the extinction coefficient generated for each SHIP1 protein sequence using ExPASy's ProtParam online calculation tool.

Biophysical Assays:

Size-Exclusion Chromatography coupled with Multi-Angle light scattering (SEC-MALS): SEC-MALS was utilized to determine the molecular weight (M.W.) and oligomeric state of SHIP1 constructs in solution at micromolar concentrations. Protein concentrations were determined using a Biotek Take3. Protein samples were loaded as 100 μ L volumes and separated using a SRT SEC-300 column (Sepax) in SEC-MALS buffer (*Table 5*.) SEC-MALS was performed at 4 $^{\circ}$ C with a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min. ASTRA software was used to calculate the molecular weight of each SHIP1 construct.

Mass Photometry Analysis: Mass-photometry was utilized to calculate the M.W. and oligomeric states of SHIP1 constructs in solution at nM concentrations. Protein concentrations were determined using a Biotek Take3. SHIP1 protein solutions at a concentration of 100 nM were prepared in REFEYN buffer (*Table 5*.) All analyses took place on a clean coverslip containing a rubber gasket. 15 μ L of Refeyn buffer was added to the rubber gasket well and the Mass-photometry lens was focused. 3 μ L of the 100nM SHIP1 protein solution was added to the drop and mixed using a pipette. Data was collected over 1 minute. The molecular weight of SHIP1 proteins were calculated using a calibration curve made with proteins of known molecular weight.

Crystallization and X-ray data collection: The SHIP1 Ptase-C2 protein construct was crystallized using a previously established crystal condition (PDB – 6IBD, 17-22% PEG 2000MME, 7-10% PEG 3000, 0.1M BIS-Tris pH 7.0.) Protein crystallization was performed in 24-well sitting drop plates by preparing drops (final volume of 3 μ L) as a 1:1 ratio of protein to reservoir solution. Crystals were allowed to grow for at least 1 week at room temperature. Crystals with sizes amenable for X-ray data collection were then cryoprotected with 2.5 μ L of cryosolution (90% reservoir solution + 10% PEG 400.) Crystals were harvested with nylon loops and flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen. X-ray data collection was performed at the LS-CAT beamline at the Advanced Photon Source, Argonne National Laboratory. Several high-resolution datasets (1.4-2.1 \AA) were obtained. Crystals of SHIP1-ligand complexes were prepared using similar methods described above, except SHIP1 was pre-incubated with inhibitor at 10-times the determined

IC₅₀ value for at least 4 hours. In addition, the crystallization solutions were optimized and ligand-bound SHIP1 structures resulted using 17-22% PEG 2000MME, 7-10% PEG 3000, 0.1M HEPES @ pH 7.0 as the crystallization solution. Ligand density was identified using difference Fo-Fc difference electron density maps and the X-ray structure of SHIP1 (PDB:6IBD) that had all of the waters and ligands removed from the coordinate file.

Figure 1. Four SHIP1 constructs (1 thru 4) were designed for biochemical, biophysical and X-ray structure analysis. These constructs were designed based on the primary sequence of SHIP1 deposited into uniprot and using protein primary sequence homology. All constructs were designed and codon-optimized for baculovirus expression. P2 viral stocks of each construct were generated by Genscript, except for construct 4 (Ptase-C2). The baculovirus expression plasmid for the SHIP1 Ptase-C2 protein was a generous gift from Dr. Opher Gileadi (University of Oxford).

Table 4		
Construct	Protein Sequence	M.W.
Ptase-C2 Protein Sequence before Tag removal	MGHHHHHHSSMSPILGYWKIKGLVQPTRLLLEYLEEKYEEHLYERDEGDKWR NKKFELGLEFPNLPYYIDGDVKLTQSMARIYIADKHNMLGGCPKERAISMLE GAVLDIRYGVSRIAYSKDFETLKVDFLSKLPEMLKMFEDRLCHKTYLNGDHVT HPDFMLYDALDVVLYMDPMCLDAFPKLVCFKKRIEAIQIDKYLKSSKYIAWP LQGWQATFGGGDHPPKSSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMEQPEPDMITIFIGTWNM GNAPPPKITSWFLSKGQGKTRDDSADYIPHDIIYVIGTQEDPLSEKEWLEILKH SLQEITSVTFKTVAIHTLWNIRIVVLAKPEHENRISHICTDNVKTGIANTLGNGK AVGVFSFMNGTSLGFVNSHLTSGSEKKLRRNQNYMNILRFLALGDKKLSFNI THRFTHLFWFGDLNRYVDLPTWEAETIIQKIKQQYADLLSHDQLLTERREQK VFLHFEEEEITFAPTYRFERLTRDKYAYTKQKATGMKYNLPSWCDRVLWKSYP LVHVVCQSYGSTSDIMTSDHSPVFATFEAGVTSQFVSKNGPGTVDSQGGQIEF LRCYATLKTQSQTKFYLFHSSCLESFVKSQEGENEEGSEGELVVKFGETLPKPK PIISDPEYLLDQHILISIKSSDSDESYGEGCIALRLEATETQLPIYTPLTHHGELTGH FQGEIKLQTSQ	81077.39
Ptase-C2 Protein Sequence after Tag removal	SMEQPEPDMITIFIGTWNMGNAPPPKITSWFLSKGQGKTRDDSADYIPHD YVIGTQEDPLSEKEWLEILKHSQEITSVTFKTVAIHTLWNIRIVVLAKPEHENR SHICTDNVKTGIANTLGNGKAVGVFSFMNGTSLGFVNSHLTSGSEKKLRRNQ NYMNILRFLALGDKKLSFNITHRFTHLFWFGDLNRYVDLPTWEAETIIQKIKQ QQYADLLSHDQLLTERREQKVFLHFEEEEITFAPTYRFERLTRDKYAYTKQKAT GMKYNLPSWCDRVLWKSYPVHVVCQSYGSTSDIMTSDHSPVFATFEAGVT SQFVSKNGPGTVDSQGGQIEFLRCYATLKTQSQTKFYLFHSSCLESFVKSQEGE NEEGSEGELVVKFGETLPKPKPIISDPEYLLDQHILISIKSSDSDES YEGCIALRLEATETQLPIYTPLTHHGELTGHFQGEIKLQTSQ	52812.79

PH-Ptase-C2 Protein Sequence before Tag removal	MHHHHHHGVDLGTENLYFQSNRPSLIPPVTFEVKAESLGIPQKMQLKVDVES GKLIKKSKDGSSEDKFYSHKKILQLIKSQKFLNKLVLVETEKEKILRKEYVFADSK KREGFCQLLQQMKNKHSEQPEPDMITIFIGTWNMGNAPPPKITSWFLSKG QGKTRDDSADYIPHDIYVIGTQEDPLSEKEWLEILKHSLEITSVTFKTVAIHTL WNIRIVVLAKPEHENRISHICTDNVKTGIANTLGNKGAVGVSFMFNGTSLGFV NSHLTSGSEKKLRRNQNYMNI LRFLALGDKKLS PFNITHRFTHLFWFGDLNVR VDLPTWEAETIIQKIKQQQYADLLSHDQLLTERREQKVFHFEEEEITFAPTYRF ERLTRDKYAYTKQKATGMKYNLPSWCDRVLWKSYPVHVVCQSYGSTSDIM TSDHSPVFATFEAGVTSQFVSKNGPGTVDSQGGQIEFLRCYATLKTKSQTKFYLE FHSSCLESFVKSQEGENE EGSEGELVVKFGETLPKPKPIISDPEYLLDQHILISIKS SDSDESYGEGCIALRLEATETQLPIYTPLTHHGELTGHFQGEIKLQTSQG	67327.71
PH-Ptase-C2 Protein Sequence after Tag removal	SNRPSLIPPVTFEVKAESLGIPQKMQLKVDVESGKLIKKSKDGSSEDKFYSHKKIL QLIKSQKFLNKLVLVETEKEKILRKEYVFADSKKREGFCQLLQQMKNKHSEQP EPDMITIFIGTWNMGNAPPPKITSWFLSKGQGKTRDDSADYIPHDIYVIGTQ EDPLSEKEWLEILKHSLEITSVTFKTVAIHTLWNIRIVVLAKPEHENRISHICTD NVKTGIANTLGNKGAVGVSFMFNGTSLGFVNSHLTSGSEKKLRRNQNYMNI LRFLALGDKKLS PFNITHRFTHLFWFGDLNVRVDLPTWEAETIIQKIKQQQYA DLLSHDQLLTERREQKVFHFEEEEITFAPTYRFERLTRDKYAYTKQKATGMKY NLP SWCDRVLWKSYPVHVVCQSYGSTSDIMTSDHSPVFATFEAGVTSQFVS KNGPGTVDSQGGQIEFLRCYATLKTKSQTKFYLEFHSSCLESFVKSQEGENE EG SEGELVVKFGETLPKPKPIISDPEYLLDQHILISIKSSDSDESYGEGCIALRLEATET QLPIYTPLTHHGELTGHFQGEIKLQTSQG	65036.22
SH2-PH-Ptase-C2 Protein Sequence before Tag removal	MHHHHHHGVDLGTENLYFQSNVPCWNHGNITRSKAEELLSRTGKDG SFLVR ASESISRAYALCVLYRNCVYTYRILPNEDDKFTVQASEGVSMRFFTKLDQLIEFY KKENMGLVTHLQYPVPLEEEDTGDDPEEDTVESVVSPPPELPPRNIPLTASSCE AKEVPFSNENPRATETS RPSLSETLFRQLQSMDT SGLPEEHLKAIQDY LSTQLA QDSEFVKTGSSSLPHLKKLTTLLCKELYGEVIRTLPSLES LQRLFDQQLSPGLRPR PQVPGEANPINMVSKLSQLTSLSSIEDKVKALLHEGPESPHRPSLIPPVTFEVK AESLGIPQKMQLKVDVESGKLIKKSKDGSSEDKFYSHKKILQLIKSQKFLNKLVL VETEKEKILRKEYVFADSKKREGFCQLLQQMKNKHSEQPEPDMITIFIGTWN MGNAPPPKITSWFLSKGQGKTRDDSADYIPHDIYVIGTQEDPLSEKEWLEIL KHSLEITSVTFKTVAIHTLWNIRIVVLAKPEHENRISHICTDNVKTGIANTLGN KGAVGV SFMFNGTSLGFVNSHLTSGSEKKLRRNQNYMNI LRFLALGDKKLS P FNITHRFTHLFWFGDLNVRVDLPTWEAETIIQKIKQQQYADLLSHDQLLTER EQKVFHFEEEEITFAPTYRFERLTRDKYAYTKQKATGMKYNLPSWCDRVLW KSYPLVHVVCQSYGSTSDIMTSDHSPVFATFEAGVTSQFVSKNGPGTVDSQG QIEFLRCYATLKTKSQTKFYLEFHSSCLESFVKSQEGENE EGSEGELVVKFGETL PKPKPIISDPEYLLDQHILISIKSSDSDESYGEGCIALRLEATETQLPIYTPLTHHG ELTGHFQGEIKLQTSQG	99802.39

<p>SH2-PH-Ptase-C2</p> <p>Protein Sequence after Tag removal</p>	<p>SNVPCWNHGNITRSKAEELLSRTGKDG SFLVRASESISRAYALCVLYRNCVYTYRILPNEDDKFTVQASEGVSMRFFTKLDQLIEFYKKENMGLVTHLQYPVPLEEEEDTGD DPEEDTVESVVSPPPELPPRNIPLTASSCEAKEVPFSNENPRATETSRPSLSETLF QRLQSMDSGLPEEHLKAIQDYLS TQLAQDSEFVKTGSSSLPHLKKLTTLLCKE LYGEVIRTLPSLES LQRLFDQQLSPGLRPRPQVPGEANPINMVS KLSQLTSLLSS IEDKVKALLHEGPESPHRPSLIPPVT FEVKAESLGIPQKMQLKVDVESGKLI IKKSKDGSEDKFYSHKILQLIKSQKFLNKL VILVETEKEKILRKEYVFADSKKREG FCQLLQQMKNKHSEQPEPDMITIFIGTWNMGNAPPPKITSWFLSKGQGKTRDD SADYIPHDIYVIGTQEDPLSEKEWLEILK HSLQEITSVTFKTVAIHTLWNIRIVVL AKPEHENRISHICTDNVKTGIANTLG NKGAVGV SFMFNGTSLGFVNSHLTSGS EKKLRRNQNYMNILRFLALGDKKLSPFNITHRFTHLFWFGDLN YRVDLPTWE AETIIQKIKQQYADLLSHDQLLTERREQVFLHFEEEEITFAPTYR FERLTRDK YAYTKQKATGMKYNLPSWCDRVLWKS YPLVHVVCQSYGSTSDIMTSDHSPV FATFEAGVTSQFVSKNGPGTVDSQGGQIEFLRCYATLKT KSQTKFYLFHSSCLE SFVKSQEGENE EGSEGELVVKFGETLPKLP IISDPEYLLDQHILISIKSSDSESY GEGCIALRLEATETQLPIYTPLTHHGELTGHFQGEIKLQTSQ GKTRKLYDFVKT ERDESSGPKTLKSLTSHDPMKQWEVTSRAPP CSGSSITEIINPNYMGVGPFGP PMPLHVKQTLSPDQQPTAWSYDQPPKDSPLGPCRGES PPTPPGQPPISP KKF LPSTANRGLPRTQESRPSDLGKNAGDTLPQEDLPLTKPEMFENPLYGSLSSF PKPAPRKDQESPMPRKEPPPCPEPGILSPSIVLTKAQEA DRGEGPGKQVPAP RLRSFTCSSSAEGRAAGGDKSQGKPKTPVSSQAPVPAKRPIKPSRSEINQQTP PTPTPRPPLPVKSPAVLHLQHSKGRDYRDNTELP H HGKHRPEEGPPGLGRT AMQ</p>	<p>97510.9</p>
<p>Full-Length Protein Sequence before Tag removal</p>	<p>SNNHGNITRSKAEELLSRTGKDG SFLVRASESISRAYALCVLYRNCVYTYRILPN EDDKFTVQASEGVSMRFFTKLDQLIEFYKKENMGLVTHLQYPVPLEEEDTGD DPEEDTVESVVSPPPELPPRNIPLTASSCEAKEVPFSNENPRATETSRPSLSETLF QRLQSMDSGLPEEHLKAIQDYLS TQLAQDSEFVKTGSSSLPHLKKLTTLLCKE LYGEVIRTLPSLES LQRLFDQQLSPGLRPRPQVPGEANPINMVS KLSQLTSLLSS IEDKVKALLHEGPESPHRPSLIPPVT FEVKAESLGIPQKMQLKVDVESGKLI IKKSKDGSEDKFYSHKILQLIKSQKFLNKL VILVETEKEKILRKEYVFADSKKREG FCQLLQQMKNKHSEQPEPDMITIFIGTWNMGNAPPPKITSWFLSKGQGKTRDD SADYIPHDIYVIGTQEDPLSEKEWLEILK HSLQEITSVTFKTVAIHTLWNIRIVVL AKPEHENRISHICTDNVKTGIANTLG NKGAVGV SFMFNGTSLGFVNSHLTSGS EKKLRRNQNYMNILRFLALGDKKLSPFNITHRFTHLFWFGDLN YRVDLPTWE AETIIQKIKQQYADLLSHDQLLTERREQVFLHFEEEEITFAPTYR FERLTRDK YAYTKQKATGMKYNLPSWCDRVLWKS YPLVHVVCQSYGSTSDIMTSDHSPV FATFEAGVTSQFVSKNGPGTVDSQGGQIEFLRCYATLKT KSQTKFYLFHSSCLE SFVKSQEGENE EGSEGELVVKFGETLPKLP IISDPEYLLDQHILISIKSSDSESY GEGCIALRLEATETQLPIYTPLTHHGELTGHFQGEIKLQTSQ GKTRKLYDFVKT ERDESSGPKTLKSLTSHDPMKQWEVTSRAPP CSGSSITEIINPNYMGVGPFGP PMPLHVKQTLSPDQQPTAWSYDQPPKDSPLGPCRGES PPTPPGQPPISP KKF LPSTANRGLPRTQESRPSDLGKNAGDTLPQEDLPLTKPEMFENPLYGSLSSF PKPAPRKDQESPMPRKEPPPCPEPGILSPSIVLTKAQEA DRGEGPGKQVPAP RLRSFTCSSSAEGRAAGGDKSQGKPKTPVSSQAPVPAKRPIKPSRSEINQQTP PTPTPRPPLPVKSPAVLHLQHSKGRDYRDNTELP H HGKHRPEEGPPGLGRT AMQ</p>	<p>135168.36</p>

Full- Length Protein Sequence after Tag removal	MHHHHHHGVDLGTENLYFQSNHGNITRSKAEELLSRTGKDG SFLVRASEI SRAYALCVLYRNCVYTYRILPNEDDKFTVQASEGVSMRFFTKLDQLIEFYKKEN MGLVTHLQYPVPLEEEDTGDDPEEDTVESVVSPELPPRNIPLTASSCEAKEVP FSNENPRATETS RPSLSETLFQRLQSMDSGLPEEHLKAIQDY LSTQLAQDSEF VKTGSSSLPHLKKLTLLCKELYGEVIRTLPSLES LQRLFDQQLSPGLRPRPQVP GEANPINMVSKLSQLTSLSSIEDKVKALLHEGPESPHRPSLIPPVTFEVKAESL GIPQKMQLKVDVESGKLIKKSKDGEDKFYSHKKILQLIKSQKFLNKLVLVETE KEKILRKEYVFADSKKREGFCQLLQQMKNKHSEQPEPDMITIFIGTWNMGNA PPPKITSWFLSKGQKTRDDSADYIPHDIYVIGTQEDPLSEKEWLEILKHS LQ EITSVTFKTVAIHTLWNIRIVVLAKPEHENRISHICTDNVKTGIANTLGNKGAVG VSF MFNGTSLGFVNSHLTSGSEKKLRRNQNYMNILRFLALGDKKLSPFNITHR FTHLFWFGDLNYRVDLPTWEAETIQIKIQQQYADLLSHDQQLLTERREQKVFL HFE EEEITFAPTYRFERLTRDKYAYTKQKATGMKYNLPSWCDRVLWKSYP L VH VVCQSYGSTSDIMTSDHSPVFATFEAGVTSQFVSKNGPGTVDSQGGQIEFLRCY ATLKTKSQTKFYLEFHSSCLESFVKSQEGENE EGSEGELVVKFGETLPKLP IISD PEYLLDQHILISIKSSDSDES YGEGCIALRLEATETQLPIYTPLTHHGELTGHFQ G EIKLQTSQGKTREKLYDFVKTERDESSGPKTLKSLTSHDPMKQWEVTSRAPP C SGSSITEIINPNYMGVGPFGPPMPLHVKQTLSPDQQPTAWSYDQPPKDSPLG PCRGESPPTPPGQPPISP KFKLPSTANRGLPPRTQESRPSDLGKNAGDTLPQE DLPLTKPEMFENPLYGSLSSF PKPAPRKDQESPKMPRKEPPPCPEPGILSPSIVL TKAQEADRGE GPGKQVPAPRLRSFTCSSSAEGRAAGGDKSQGKPKTPVSSQ APVPAKRPIKPSRSEINQQTPPTPTPRPPLPVKSPA VLHLQHSGKGRDYRDNTEL PHHGKHRPEEGPPGPLGRTAMQ	135168.36
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Table 5			
Purification	Buffer	Components	pH
Ptase-C2 and PH-Ptase-C2	A (HiTrap)	50mM Tris-Base, 500mM NaCl, 5% Glycerol	8
	B (HiTrap)	50mM Tris-Base, 500mM NaCl, 400mM Imidazole, 5% Glycerol	8
	C (Anion Exchange)	20mM Tris-Base	8
	D (Anion Exchange)	50mM Tris-Base, 1M NaCl	8
	E (Sizing/Storage)	50mM HEPES, 250mM NaCl, 1mM TCEP, 5% Glycerol	7.5
	Dialysis (TEV)	50mM Tris-Base, 250mM NaCl, 5% Glycerol, 5mM B-ME	8
	Dialysis (Anion Exchange)	20mM Tris-Base	8
SH2-PH-Ptase-C2 and Full-Length	A (HiTrap)	50mM Tris-Base, 500mM NaCl, 5% Glycerol	8
	B (HiTrap)	50mM Tris-Base, 500mM NaCl, 400mM Imidazole, 5% Glycerol	8
	F (Storage)	50mM HEPES, 500mM NaCl, 1mM TCEP, 5% Glycerol	7.5
	Dialysis (TEV)	50mM Tris-Base, 500mM NaCl, 5% Glycerol, 5mM B-ME	8
N/A	Crystallization/DSF	50mM HEPES, 250mM NaCl, 1mM TCEP, 5% Glycerol	7.5
	CryoEM/Refyne/SE C-MAL	50mM HEPES, 250mM NaCl, 1mM TCEP	7.5
	Phosphatase Assay	50mM HEPES, 150mM NaCl, 2mM MgCl ₂	7.4

Figure 2. SHIP1 constructs were purified using several different multi-step purification strategies including IMAC, anion-exchange, and gel-filtration chromatography. The purity of each construct was analyzed using SDS-PAGE (10% gels). Approximately 2ug of protein as loaded into each lane. **A.** SDS-PAGE analysis after the final purification step for SHIP1protein constructs Ptase-C2 (lane 2), PH-Ptase-C2 (lane 3), SH2-PH-Ptase-C2 (lane 4). **B.** SDS-PAGE analysis of purification of full-length SHIP1 (Lane 2). Molecular weight standard are shown in lane 1 for each gel and are given in kDa.

Figure 3. Generation of P1 and P2 viral stocks encoding SHIP1's Ptase-C2 domain. **A.** 120 μ L of P0 viral stock was used to infect 3 mL of 1×10^6 SF9 II cell/mL (viability >95%) in sterile 6-well plates. The plates were incubated for a total of 72 hours in an incubator set at 27 °C. SDS-PAGE analysis was used to verify SHIP1 Ptase-C2 expression in the soluble and insoluble fractions. A P0 "viral stock" generated using only cellfectin II and no Bacmid DNA served as the positive control. **B.** 100 μ L of P1 viral stock was used to infect 20 mL of 1×10^6 SF9 II cell/mL (viability >95%) in 125 mL Erlenmeyer flasks. Suspension cultures were incubated in a floor incubator set at 27 °C and shaking at 120 rpm. SDS-PAGE analysis was used to verify SHIP1 Ptase-C2 expression in the soluble and insoluble fractions. A P0 "viral stock" generated using only cellfectin II and no Bacmid DNA served as the positive control.

Figure 4. Quaternary structure analysis of SHIP1 protein constructs Ptase-C2, PH-Ptase-C2, and SH2-PH-Ptase-C2 using SEC-MALS and mass photometry. Please refer to *Table 4* for the predicted molecular weights. **A.** SEC-MALS results obtained from this experiment indicate that SHIP1 construct SH2-PH-Ptase-C2 exists as a dimer in solution at micromolar concentrations **B.** mass photometry (REFEYN, Inc.) results obtained from this experiment indicate that SHIP1 construct SH2-PH-Ptase-C2 exists as a dimer in solution as low as 10 to 20 nM concentration.

Mw (kDa)	Polydispersity (Mw/Mn)	r(avg) (nm)	Calculated mass (μg)
122758.2	1.662	73.1	4.78
(5.90%)	(6.32%)	(0.00%)	(100%)

Figure 5. SEC-MALS analysis of the purified, full-length SHIP1 protein. Results indicate the protein is highly aggregated.

Figure 6. X-ray structures of three SHIP1 (Ptase-C2) crystallized with different ligands and under slightly different conditions. **A.** Unbound SHIP1 structure determined to 2.1 Å. The phosphatase domain is colored in red and the C2 domain is colored in green. A glycerol molecule was modeled in between the Ptase and C2 domains. **B.** A magnesium (II) and phosphate bound structure of SHIP1 was determined to 1.6 Å. Both magnesium and phosphate can be found bound within the active site of the phosphatase domain. **C.** X-ray structure of SHIP1 Ptase-C2 modified with a covalent inhibitor determined to 1.8 Å. The molecule was found to be covalently bound to Cysteine 504 which is between the Ptase and C2 domains.

INPP5D Construct	K _m (μM)	k _{cat} (s ⁻¹)	k _{cat} /K _m (s ⁻¹ M ⁻¹)	n _H (Hi II)	Predicted Molecular Weight	Determined Quaternary Structure
Ptase	42.7 ± 8.3	1.36 ± 0.18	(3.19 ± 0.06) × 10 ⁵			
Ptase+C2	25.1 ± 0.9	4.2 ± 0.1	(1.68 ± 0.06) × 10 ⁵	2.1 ± 0.1	53 kDa	Monomer (SEC-MALS)
PH+Ptase+C2	23.5 ± 0.7	3.8 ± 0.1	(1.63 ± 0.05) × 10 ⁵	2.3 ± 0.1	65 kDa	Monomer (SEC-MALS)
SH2+PH+Ptase+C2	26.7 ± 1.2	3.3 ± 0.1	(1.24 ± 0.06) × 10 ⁵	2.1 ± 0.2	98 kDa	Dimer (SEC-MALS)
Full Length	37.0 ± 2.4	1.06 ± 0.03	(0.29 ± 0.02) × 10 ⁵	1.7 ± 0.1	133 kDa	

Assay Methods and Screening

Introduction

Src Homology 2-containing Inositol 5'- Phosphatase-1 (SHIP-1), encoded by *INPP5D*, is selectively expressed in brain microglia.⁶ SHIP-1 plays a critical negative role in triggering receptor expressed on myeloid cells 2 (TREM2) signaling pathway,⁷ which promotes the optimal microglial function required to attenuate AD progression.⁸ Increased expression of SHIP-1 in brain has been associated with late-onset Alzheimer' Disease, the most common form of Alzheimer' Disease (AD).⁹ However, the detailed role of SHIP-1 in AD onset and progression remains unclear. Although several small molecules have been reported to modulate SHIP-1, the lack of efficacy in advanced models highly limited these compounds as potential therapeutics or probes for biological studies.¹⁰ To address this critical need, we developed and implemented a high-throughput screen platform to explore new chemotypes that modulate SHIP-1 catalytic domain activity. We screened 93,516 diverse small molecules sourced from commercial vendors using a malachite green-based assay for anti-SHIP-1 activity. Through analysis, prioritization, and validation of the screening hits, we identified 3 types of novel scaffolds that inhibit SHIP-1 phosphatase domain with IC₅₀s as low as 16.8 μM.

Screening Strategy

We first optimized the previously reported PtdIns(3,4,5)P₃-diC₈ malachite green coupled assay¹¹ for the use in 384-well plates. An "excellent-range" Z' score of 0.84 was determined for the assay. Subsequently, nearly 95,000 compounds were screened in order to identify potential scaffolds for lead development. To accomplish this, first a virtual screen was performed against the catalytical site of SHIP-1 and the compounds contained within Purdue's compound collection. The library plates with the highest scoring compounds from the virtual screen were chosen for the initial 50,176 compound HT screen. An additional 43,340 compounds were within the CNS-biased libraries within Purdue's compound collection then were screened. All compounds were screened at 10 μM with the catalytic domain of SHIP-1, which should bias the screen to identify active site (i.e. orthosteric) inhibitors.

SHIP-1 and SHIP-2 protein purification:

The catalytic domains of human SHIP-1 and SHIP-2 were cloned into the pET-21a vector. The catalytic domain construct used for SHIP-1 was from 397-715 amino acid residues. The catalytic

domain used for SHIP-2 was from 420-732 amino acid residues. The proteins were purified in Rosetta DE3 BL21 cells. The cells were grown at 37 °C (while shaking at 200 rpm) until the OD reached between 0.6-0.8. Next, protein production was induced using 0.5mM IPTG. The protein induction was carried out for 20 hours at 18 °C (while shaking at 180 rpm). Then, the bacterial cells were harvested by centrifugation at 5500 rpm for 15 minutes. The bacterial pellet was dissolved in 20 mM HEPES, 5 mM Imidazole, 500 mM NaCl pH 7 with 1 mM PMSF. Next, the cells were lysed through sonication. The cell lysate was then centrifuged at 14,000 rpm for 30 minutes to remove cell debris. The supernatant was incubated with Ni-NTA resin (Qiagen). The standard affinity purification protocol was followed using the Qiagen handbook. The protein elution was concentrated using Millipore Amicon Ultra centrifugal filter device. The purified protein was stored in 20 mM HEPES, 300 mM NaCl pH 7. The purity of the purified protein was assessed using an SDS PAGE gel. The purified protein was then aliquoted and flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored in -80 °C.

The SHIP-1 catalytic domain purified protein was run on an SDS PAGE and stained with Gel Code Blue (Figure 7A). The SHIP-2 catalytic domain purified protein was run on an SDS PAGE and stained with Gel Code Blue (Figure 7B). The SHIP-1 catalytic domain had a very low yield since the protein was insoluble and the majority was in the pellet (insoluble fraction). Around 12-20 L of bacterial culture was necessary to obtain around 3-4 mg of protein. Additionally, we found that autoinduction at 18 °C yielded the best soluble protein expression. Since the His-Ni Column elution was not pure, a downstream ion exchange column (HiTrapQHP) and a size exclusion column (S75 or S200) were run to get protein more than 90% purity. The SHIP-2 catalytic domain was much more soluble and had a higher yield of around 10 mg of protein per L of LB. The purified protein was then used to characterize its kinetic activity using PtdIns(3,4,5)P3-diC8 as the substrate.

Figure 7. Purification of SHIP-1 and SHIP-2 protein. A. Purification flow off of SHIP-1 catalytic domain. After His-Ni Column, the elution was used to run an ion exchange column (HiTrapQ HP) followed by size exclusion chromatography S75. B. Purification flow off of SHIP-2 catalytic domain. The protein was concentrated after His-Ni Column.

High Throughput Screening Protocol:

The single point inhibition rates were obtained by using PtdIns(3,4,5)P3-diC8 as a substrate at 25 °C in pH7.4 HEPES buffer(150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂). Compounds were pre-transferred to 384-well plates by Echo 550 liquid handler (Labcyte)(10 μM final concentration). 10 μL of PtdIns(3,4,5)P3-diC8 solution was added to each well. The reaction was then initiated by adding 25 μL of the enzyme solution. The final reaction concentrations for compounds, PtdIns(3,4,5)P3-diC8, and the enzyme were 10 μM, 45 μM, and 50 nM correspondingly. The reaction was quenched after 5 min by the addition of 40 μL of Malachite green reagent (Biomol, PA, USA). And then the plates were incubated for another 25 min at room temperature. Absorbance at 620 nm was measured using a SpectraMax Plus 384 Microplate Reader (Molecular Devices, LLC, USA). The inhibition rates for the compounds were calculated.

HTS results:

As summarized in Table 6, 208 primary hits were identified that inhibited SHIP-1's catalytic activity > 50% and were designated as Tier 1 hits. An additional 376 primary hits were identified that inhibited SHIP-1's activity > 30%, but less than 50 % and were designated as Tier 2 hits. The Tier 1 hits were prioritized and subjected to cheminformatics analyses that eliminated compounds with substructures found within the PAINS databases, are known promiscuous binders, and/or strong electrophiles such as Michael acceptors. Next, hits with similar structures were grouped into series with a total of 16 hit series identified from the Tier 1 hits. Next, 70 compounds encompassing the original hits and closely related analogues were purchased. Their structure and purity were confirmed by LC-MS and their ability to inhibit SHIP-1 was confirmed. Of the 16 hit series, 8 reproduced their inhibitory activity at 100 μM (Figure 8A).

Table 6. HTS hits identified from each compound library. Tier 1 hits >50% inhibition at 10 μ M Concentration; Tier 2 hits = 30% ~50% inhibition at 10 μ M Concentration

Library ID	Number of tier 1 hits	Number of tier 2 hits
ACM1K	23	37
ACN5K	10	15
CB_30K	0	0
CB_50K	8	28
CB_Fragment	0	0
CB_GPCR	0	0
CB_ION	0	0
CB_Kinase	0	0
CB_NHR	0	0
CBm_20K_CNS	33	37
CBm_30K_DIVERSET	0	3
CD_10K	1	2
CD_60K	14	47
ChemBridge43K	31	77
ChemDiv55K	43	97
CNS_ChemDiv	8	20
CNS_Enamine	1	0
CNS_LC	3	3
CNS_OTAVA	0	0
CNS_TimTec	3	2
LC_50K	0	0
LC_CP_29K_m	0	0
LC_Fragment_PPI	0	0
LC_Fragment_Sol	0	0
LOPAC2016	6	9
SP2400	26	41

A

B

Figure 8. Compound's structures of HTS hits. A. Representative compounds' structures in the 8 series of HTS hits that reproduce inhibitory activity at 100 μM . B. Structures of 3 series of compounds with their IC_{50} s.

Hit Validation

To determine if any of these hit series exerted their inhibitory effects through an aggregation mechanism, a common but undesirable mode of action, their IC_{50} values against SHIP-1 were measured in the presence and absence of the detergent Triton X-100. For five of these series, their inhibitory activity was significantly abolished by the addition of the detergent. The C4, C10, and C12 series of compounds were unaffected (Figure 8B). Furthermore, the compounds in these 3 series showed clear inhibitory selectivity of SHIP-1 over SHIP-2, which are close paralogs in the inositol 5'-Phosphatase (SHIP) enzyme family. Therefore, these 3 series were advanced to the MCCB core for retrosynthetic analysis, structure-activity-relationship (SAR) studies, and derivation.

SHIP-1(Catalytic Domain=Ptase) IC_{50} test protocol:

Buffer: 50 mM HEPES Buffer (pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl_2). Substrate: 1-(1,2-dioctanoylphosphatidyl)inositol-3,4,5-trisphosphate, tetrasodium salt (Cayman Chemical, Item No. 10007764). The IC_{50} values of the inhibitors were assayed using $\text{PtdIns}(3,4,5)\text{P}_3$ -diC8 as a substrate at 25 $^\circ\text{C}$ in pH7.4 HEPES buffer (150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl_2). The compounds were

serial diluted in 96-well plates and yielded compound solutions with final concentrations ranging from 1 μM to 100 μM . Then, 25 μL of PtdIns(3,4,5)P₃-diC8 solution was added. The reaction was initiated by adding 25 μL of the enzyme solution. The final reaction concentrations for PtdIns(3,4,5)P₃-diC8 and the enzyme were 45 μM and 50 nM correspondingly. The reaction was quenched after 5 min by the addition of 200 μL of Malachite green reagent (Biomol, PA, USA). And then the plates were incubated for another 25 min at room temperature. Absorbance at 620 nm was measured using a SpectraMax Plus 384 Microplate Reader (Molecular Devices, LLC, USA). IC₅₀ values for the compounds were calculated by fitting the absorbance at 620 nm versus inhibitor concentration.

Detergent Assay (weed out aggregators) Protocol:

Buffer: 50 mM HEPES Buffer (pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂, 0.01% Triton X-100).
Substrate: 1-(1,2-dioctanoylphosphatidyl)inositol-3,4,5-trisphosphate, tetrasodium salt (Cayman Chemical, Item No. 10007764). The IC₅₀ values of compounds were determined by using PtdIns(3,4,5)P₃-diC8 as a substrate at 25 °C in 50 mM HEPES Buffer (pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂, 0.01% Triton X-100). The compounds were serial diluted in 96-well plates and yielded compound solutions (50 μL). Then 25 μL of PtdIns(3,4,5)P₃-diC8 solution was added. The reaction was initiated by adding 25 μL of the enzyme solution. The final reaction concentrations for PtdIns(3,4,5)P₃-diC8 and the enzyme are 30 μM and 100 nM correspondingly. The reaction was quenched after 4 min by adding 200 μL of Malachite BioMol Green (Enzo Lifesciences, PA, USA). And then the plates were incubated for another 25 min. at room temperature. Absorbance at 620 nm was measured using a SpectraMax Plus 384 Microplate Reader (Molecular Devices, LLC, USA). IC₅₀ values for the compounds were calculated by fitting the absorbance at 620 nm versus inhibitor concentration.

SHIP-2 (Catalytic Domain=Ptase) IC₅₀ (Counter-Screen) protocol:

Buffer: 50 mM HEPES Buffer (pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂). Substrate: 1-(1,2-dioctanoylphosphatidyl)inositol-3,4,5-trisphosphate, tetrasodium salt (Cayman Chemical, Item No. 10007764). The IC₅₀ values of compounds were determined by using PtdIns(3,4,5)P₃-diC8 as a substrate at 25 °C in 50 mM HEPES buffer (pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂). The compounds were serial diluted in 96-well plates and yielded compound solutions (50 μL). Then, 25 μL of PtdIns(3,4,5)P₃-diC8 solution was added. The reaction was initiated by adding 25 μL of the enzyme solution. The final reaction concentrations for PtdIns(3,4,5)P₃-diC8 and the enzyme were 30 μM and 100 nM correspondingly. The reaction was quenched after 4 min. by adding 200 μL of Malachite BioMol Green (Enzo Lifesciences, PA, USA). And then the plates were incubated for another 25 min. at room temperature. Absorbance at 620 nm was measured using a SpectraMax

Plus 384 Microplate Reader (Molecular Devices, LLC, USA). IC₅₀ values for the compounds were calculated by fitting the absorbance at 620 nm versus inhibitor concentration.

Cell-Based Assays:

The validated HTS hits were evaluated for their ability to promote phagocytosis in microglia cells. The compounds were tested in both human microglial clone 3 cell line (HMC3) and murine microglial cell line (BV-2). The compound TAD-0058583 showed an EC₅₀ of 9.9 μM on enhancing phagocytosis in BV-2 cells, while other experimental trials resulted in trivial or no activity. At concentrations that promote phagocytosis, the inhibitor was non-toxic at 48 hours. This data showed early evidence that the inhibitor can promote human microglia-like cell phagocytosis.

pHrodo-myelin phagocytosis/cell viability assay with microglial cells:

The 384-well plate high content assay with BV2 and HMC3 immortalized microglial cell lines was developed to quantify phagocytosis and cell viability simultaneously. BV2 and HMC3 cells were cultured with DMEM GlutaMax media (ThermoFisher) that contained 10% FBS and Pen-Strep in a 37 °C 5% CO₂ incubator. Compound stocks were 20 mM in DMSO stored in a -20 °C or -80 °C freezer. The assay was also used with primary microglia isolated from mouse brain, but cells were plated at 2000 cell/45μl/well into a 384 well plate. Following our assay procedures, all liquid handling steps were performed with an automatic system, the OPENTRONs OT2 system was used in the lab.

Day 1: Cells were plated in 384-well plates (Corning Falcon 384 well Optilux Black and clear bottom plates, or similar plates for cellular imaging) with BV2 at 400 cells/45μl/well and HMC3 at 600 cells/45μL/well.

Day 2: Cells were treated with compounds for a total of 48 hours. For treating cells, 10x compound serial dilutions were prepared. Typically, wells were started by adding 3 μL of the 20 mM stock into 97 μL media resulting in 600 μM and 3% DMSO, then were serial diluted in 1:3 (transferred and mixed 30 μL to next well with 60 μL media containing 3% DMSO) in 96 well compound plate, total 10 points. 5 μL/well of the 10x compounds were transferred to cell plates with 45 μL/well cells resulting in a dose range of 60 μM to 3 nM 10 points treatments. Duplicates of each compound treatment were regularly performed with the 384 well assay. Cell plates were then returned to the 37 °C incubator.

Day 3: Cells were seeded with pHrodo-myelin (for a total of 20 hours) 24 hours after starting compound treatment. The pHrodo-myelin stocks were at 1mg/ml (protein equivalent) stored in -20 °C or -80 °C freezer. A stock and dilution of the stock (with culture media) were thawed into

10x seeding solution (50 µg/mL), and added 5 µL/well to 384 well cell plate. Seeded plates were returned to the 37 °C incubator.

Day 4: Stain cell with Hoechst-33342 and imaging. The nuclear staining solution was prepared by adding 1 µL of 10 mM Hoechst-33342 to every 1 mL culture media used in the cell plate at 20 µL/well, the final concentration of Hoechst-33342 to cells was about 2.5 µg/mL. Cell plates were incubated for > 30 min in the 37 °C incubator before imaging.

Cell plates were scanned with ArrayScan automatic high content imaging system using a 10x objective lens, 4 fields/well were collected. Three measurements were extracted from the assay, 1) phagocytosis signal by mean total phagocytosis spot intensity per cell, 2) total cell counts per well as the main measurement of cell viability, and 3) mean average nuclear intensity per cell as profiling of cell health since apoptotic cells showing nuclear intensity increase (early apoptosis) and decrease (later apoptosis) respectively.

Data analysis: Mean of untreated controls were calculate for normalization. Raw data was normalized to controls, % phagocytosis was calculated with $100 \times (X - \text{Min}) / (\text{Max} - \text{Min})$, where the X was raw data from a well, Min was mean from control unseeded wells and Max was mean from control pHrodo-myelin seeded wells. Cell counts and nuclear intensity were % of untreated wells respectively. Normalized data was analyzed with the Prism software for dose response curve fitting and potency determination.

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